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NODE CENTRALITY AND ROAD ACCESSIBILITY IN MOUNTAINOUS AREA: A STUDY OF AIZAWL DISTRICT, MIZORAM

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Abstract : *This study explores diverse methods to quantify node centrality in networks. The approach focuses on direct and indirect node interactions, investigating their influence on centrality and road network accessibility in hilly areas. Such an approach allows us to elucidate how a node is structurally connected to other nodes in the network and its components. The research establishes metrics for assessing node centrality in hilly road networks using specific measures. It highlights critical nodes, linking spatial interactions, centrality, and accessibility. By utilizing geospatial technology, the study maps node centrality in the Aizawl district, potentially guiding road network design to effectively address transportation and resource allocation issues.*

Keywords : *Centrality measure, Node Centrality, Accessibility, Spatial network*

1. Introduction

In road network analysis, networks (agents of flow) and nodes (origins and destinations) play fundamental roles as they facilitate movement between locations. However, a node on its own lacks significance and only gains value within connections (transport network). Nodes are important when well-connected by a transport network, making centrality and accessibility crucial in completing a transport network (Raut, 2015). Centrality, a fundamental concept in network analysis, aims to measure a node's relative 'importance' within a network. The road network system represents the communication mode, serving as a means of centrality, while the node is recognized as the center of diffusion within a complex network system in the area (Garrison and Marble, 1965). Transport networks enhance the

efficiency of people and goods moving in various directions, improving accessibility for each node within the network. The study of road networks involves analyzing the distribution of centrality and its attributes across space in different dimensions, asserting that some places are more crucial due to their central nature. The study of transport networks primarily focuses on centrality measures for node analysis, their spatial distribution, and arrangement, which significantly contribute to local and global attraction (Wilson, 2000).

The intensity of interaction through vertices determines the degree of relationship between geographical spaces. Ullman's (1957 and 1980) three basic spatial interactions - complementary, transferability, and intervening opportunity - define different systems of linkages and connectivity at various scales,

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generating spatial relationships. Transportation nodes and vertices are essential elements and links for interactions in geographical space, creating definitive relationships between spaces. The degree of interconnections may vary across perspectives and time periods, considering geographic, economic, social, and technical disparities. Geography consistently aims to analyze and interpret the relationships between spatial features and their patterns of interaction within specific geographical space. The diverse modes of interaction evolve over time and space, leading to significant modifications in interaction systems and patterns due to shifts in geographical, technological, and socio-economic elements. As time and space change, the varying interaction modes undergo changes, resulting in substantial alterations in interaction systems and patterns. Likewise, in recent decades, transport geographers have endeavored to successfully outline spatial interaction patterns through network analysis. Notably, geographical constraints in specific regions might lead to limited connectivity between spaces, presenting significant spatial interaction challenges. Conversely, geographical advantages can confer centralization and enhanced accessibility on certain areas. Consequently, road transportation has become the primary mode for the masses in the Aizawl district. Evaluating the effectiveness of the road transport network is essential to comprehend its role in spatial interaction regarding centrality and accessibility. This inquiry

forms a foundation for policy-makers, planners, stakeholders, and further research in both Mizoram and particularly Aizawl district.

Centrality measures are crucial for defining node identities, attributes, network structural attributes, and network topological attributes. Central places or nodes seem to possess spatial advantages, benefiting local communities with improved transportation and socio-economic facilities. Recently, the focus has shifted towards distributing centrality values across all nodes (Crucitti et al., 2006; Chen et al., 2014; Ford et al., 2015). Centrality is a key property in complex network systems, transforming surrounding geographic space into point, linear, and spatial centrality forms. Similarly, node, linear, and spatial centrality are dynamic concepts that are not mutually exclusive, varying from one perspective to another and at different stages (Devkota, 2015). Centrality potentially determines node attributes, with some being relatively stronger than those of other spatial units in the region. Strong centrality can be attributed to the scale of attributes (Mavoia et al., 2012; Li et al., 2017). The centrality of a node is greatly influenced by its attributes and the distance from other nodes, taking into account geographical proximity and spatial distance.

The study employed centrality measurements to evaluate the accessibility of nodes or regions, drawing from Freeman's concept of social network analysis. Node accessibility, in this context, pertains to assessing the extent

of openness that generates interaction or potential interaction between a specific vertex and other vertices in the network through the shortest path (Porta, 2006; Belén et al., 2021). Additionally, a node is considered central and accessible when situated between other nodes. This position influences shortest paths by enabling, obstructing, or otherwise impacting the flow of communication within the network (Bonacich, 1987; Holme, 2003). The efficiency of node accessibility inherently relies on network structure and topology, influenced by movement patterns, directions, and flow (Kansky, 1963; Xie, 2007; Demsar et al., 2008). Simply put, the network's topology and structure shape the attributes of node and edge centrality. In a broader perspective, centrality's concept reveals the roles and identities of nodes and edges within the network system, considering nodes as common resources accessible from any point through edges (Garrison and Marble, 1965; Kilicman and Abdu, 2018).

Theoretically, in a transport network, access is available to anyone located in the network when entry and exit is possible. The level of accessibility varies according to one's locations within the transport system (Rodrigue, 2006). Hansen (1959) defines, "accessibility is defined as the potential of opportunities for interaction". So, "an examination of the accessibility of vertices in a transportation network (a graph) is an important element in any geographical analysis of transportation systems. It is therefore becomes obvious that the network

vertices of high transportation accessibility may be considered privileged locations or places in the broader meaning of the term" (Mackiewicz and Ratajczak, 1996). The concept of accessibility connotes importance of a place and more particularly the ease with which one can commute from one place to another (Panday, 1986). But, the problem lies in the measurement of accessibility because accessibility alone is abstract in nature unless the assessment or measurement of the intensity of interactions is done by considering two subsidiary concepts – relative accessibility and integral accessibility (Ingram, 1971). Relative accessibility considered the degree of relationship between two points (or locations) on the same surface. Integral accessibility, on the other hand measures degree of interconnection of particular point with every other point on the same surface.

Geographical centrality is a dynamic concept that varies across different perspectives and stages. A spatial unit exhibits strong centrality when its average distance to other spatial units in the region is closer, often based on geographical proximity. Additionally, network characteristics may determine geographical centrality. A spatial unit possessing one or more attributes relatively stronger than other units in the region could also be considered to have strong centrality, often based on attribute scaling (Li et al., 2017). The study primarily focuses on centrality measures for analyzing spatial interaction, spatial distributions of centrality and

accessibility, and the arrangement of nodes, all of which significantly contribute to geographical centrality.

2. The Study Area

Aizawl district covers an area of 3,577 square kilometers. The district is geographically situated between 23° 18' N - 24° 25' N latitudes and 92° 37' E - 93° 11' E longitudes. Predominantly mountainous and is characterized by mountain ranges and deep river valleys with an average elevation of 1,000–1,300 meters above sea level. The mountain ranges are aligned from north to south and run parallel to one another. The ranges are separated by narrow and deep river valleys, which contribute to the rugged terrain of the area. The overall relief is higher, and the slopes are much steeper in the eastern half of the study area. The drainage systems are originated from the central parts of the state and flow either towards the north or south direction along north-south trending ridges. Aizawl district has a humid tropical climate with a short winter and a long summer season characterized by heavy monsoon rainfall. The study area has a significantly high population density of 113 persons per square kilometer, which is significantly higher than the state average density of 52 persons per square kilometer in the 2011 census. High population concentration was seen in the middle part of the district, especially along National Highway number 54, as well as along the main arterial roads. The socio-cultural characteristics are essentially uniform throughout the area

which is dominated by tribal traditions, customs and organisation systems. Aizawl is the largest and capital city of Mizoram with a population of more than 228,442 peoples. Settlements are normally built on hilltops, rural settlement patterns depend on topographical factors and urban settlement patterns are characterized by the arrangement of the transport network and the location of administrative centers, educational institutes. Recently, the spatial organization of settlements and the establishment of new settlements were closely related to transport facilities.

3. Materials and Methods

The study addressed three methodological problems, data extraction namely, data modelling, network centrality measures.

3.1 Database Design

The spatial features including point and line features are the basis of road network database design. Line features symbolize the road network, while points denote settlements or nodes. Google Earth and Open Street Map (OSM) played a significant role in obtaining these features. The extracted data were utilized to create nodes and edges in data modeling. Afterward, the extracted data underwent transformation and conversion into readable, manageable formats for further manipulation and analysis. Geometric correction was employed to mitigate topological errors. To enable in-depth analysis, the extracted

data was initially stored in the ArcGIS and QGIS database. Point features were generated based on two fundamental principles: road intersections representing nodes or villages, and line edges representing ‘dead-end connectivity’ as well as ‘dead-end nodes’. The entire network comprises 83 junctions (nodes/vertices) and 179 road segments (edges).

3.2 Data Modelling

A network model is to transformed spatial world into digital or computer based transformation. The fundamental of the network analysis is based on simple undirected graph techniques. A graph is a simple interactions and relational combination of one point to another; it can be used to represent topological space (Kilicman and Abdu, 2018). A Graph based representation of a network measures the topological possibilities or capacity of interaction of each node on the graph. Graph theory offers an opportunity to transform real world network structure in to computable platform. The study employs computation environment ‘R’ programming and Gephi statistical software and for spatial analysis and further mathematical calculations. Accordingly, topological or structural properties of network were measured with the help of centrality measures.

3.3 Centrality Measures

Watts and Strogatz (1998), Barabási and Albert (1999), Porta and Latora (2006), Rubulotta et al. (2013),

Hellervik et al. (2019), and Sahitya and Prasad (2020), discussed centrality measures as the key variables that are considered for the measurement of node accessibility. Centrality measures were utilized for simplification of the complex network system that is influenced by the topological structure of the network. The study employed network centrality measures to scrutinize each network point, directly or indirectly linked to road network topology and arrangement. Centrality measures such as Degree of centrality, closeness centrality, betweenness centrality, eigenvector centrality, and eccentricity centrality are basis of node centrality measures. The centrality values (structural attributes) of nodes were used to measure degree of accessibility of nodes of the network. Later, the study used synthesis method to simplify node accessibility and centrality analysis. For overall accessibility and centrality levels, simple statistical techniques like Mean Accessibility Index (AI) were employed.

4. Result and Analysis

In network science, every connected node or village and town has some degree of centrality. A particular node may be more important than others if it is linked with other important nodes. Node distribution facilitates the understanding and identification of critical node and vertices in the network, which is important for the characterisation and visualisation of critical nodes and vertices inside the network (Kisgyorgy and Vasvari, 2014). It also measures and

examined the magnitude of importance of a road or intersection (node) and at what level a network is centralised on certain roads (Zhang, 2011).

4.1 Degree of Centrality (C_D)

The degree of centrality is a simple mathematical representation of the degree of point that is based on the concept of adjacency matrix (Niemens, 1974 and Freeman, 1979). The C_D of a vertex v in an undirected network is the number of links connecting to a node. Degree of Centrality (C_D) represents adjacent link of vertex v in network, which is simply defined as the degree of $C_D(v)$ of a vertex v in an undirected graph (Bolland 1988, Porta 2015 and Zhang 2017). The degree of centrality (C_D) is expressed as;

$$C_D = \frac{1}{|V| - 1} \cdot \sum_{j=1}^{|V|} a_{ij} = \frac{deg(i)}{N - 1} \dots \dots (i)$$

where, $|V| = N$ represents the number of vertices, i the reference node, a_{ij} the number of the adjacent edges that originate from a node and $deg(i)$ the degree of a node. Settlements showing Very high degree of centrality like Aizawl, Sialuk, Seling and Keifang/Saitual have significant potential to control the stability, flow of information and infrastructure which in turn has critical implications on the socio-economic development of the proximity nodes. Thus it can be argued that the Very High C_D and High C_D are more attractive and are significant for controlling the flow of commodities than those in the low scoring categories (Figure 1a). The study

identified that about 86.75 per cent of villages which fell under Very Low C_D and Low C_D classes are insignificant in this network. It is important to note that settlements are aligned linearly along the direction of network which is influenced by geographical factors like the direction of mountain ranges and topographic structure which inadvertently affects the orientation of the network. Similarly, the C_D values which are measured in this study clearly indicate the nature of the terrain of the district.

4.2 Eccentricity (CE)

Eccentricity centrality index is used to determine the shortest distance of a particular node from the furthest node in the network. Mathematically, the eccentricity $e(v)$ of a vertex v in a connected graph G which is the distance between v and a vertex that are farthest from v in G , while the radius $rad(G)$ is the smallest eccentricity among the vertices of G (Soliman 2018). Settlements with less eccentricity values are more accessible than those nodes showing high values (Takes and Kusters, 2013). It is applicable for detecting the strategic locations or spatial location of facilities that provide required facilities within a short period of time in the context of a road transportation network. According to Iwabuchi et al, Degree of Eccentricity (CE) of $e(v)$ of a vertex $v \in V$ can be denoted by the following equation;

$$e(v) = \max_{w \in V} \{d(v,w)\} \dots \dots (ii)$$

where, distance $d(v,w)$ between two

vertices $v, w \in V$ is defined as the length of the shortest path between v and w . The nodes with low scoring C_e values are centrally located and easily accessible from any point. On the other hand, the spatial distribution of eccentricity values highlights that node values progressively increase away from the center in all directions. The study shows that almost 45 per cent of the nodes are critical nodes because the diameter of the node is minimum from the isolated node. The highest accessible settlements (least degree of eccentricity) mainly found in and around western part of the study area. On the other hand, the least accessible nodes showing the highest degree of eccentricity are found in eastern portion of the study area. This means that the nodes in the central and middle parts of the network are more critical and that the farthest nodes are less influential and less significant (Figure 1b). These are significant for strategic planning to monitor the entire networking system.

4.3 Closeness Centrality (C_c)

Closeness centrality measures the shortest path of a particular node to other nodes in the network. It shows how fast a particular node can be reached from all other nodes in the network. "Closeness is a rough measure of the overall position of an actor in the network, giving an idea about how long it will take to reach other nodes from a given starting node" (Oliveira and Gama, 2012). Again, closeness centrality is applicable for strategic planning for locating emergency services, public distribution systems and

public services infrastructure etc. This analysis also emphasises the distance of a prominent node (actor) to all others in the network by considering the space from each actor to the others. Then, the Closeness Centrality (C_c) is expressed as;

$$C_c(i) = \frac{N-1}{\sum_{j=1}^N d_{ij}} \dots \dots \dots (iii)$$

where, N is the total number of nodes in the network, d_{ij} is the shortest path length between node i and j . Simply, C_c measures the mean distance of vertex with other vertices through geodesic path. The calculated values are between 0 to 1; with the higher value indicating that the node is more central. As shown by the relatively higher closeness centrality value Seling is the most centrally located node in the study area. Geographically, settlements with very high and high degree of closeness centrality are generally located within the central regions of the network. Location in the central position results in the overall road network topology having better accessibility and higher degree of control compared to other settlements in the network. The settlements located in the isolated areas have poor accessibility and are difficult to reach from any other point, which means that the settlements have limited resources compared to the higher value settlements. The Figure 1 (c) illustrated that geographic centrality in the centre/middle region of the area is influenced by the network proximity. Interestingly, the high scoring nodes are surrounded by the succeeding values. It shows that the low scoring nodes are diverge in the north-south direction from

the highest centrality values in this network. The spatial arrangement that emerges also reveals that nodes are arranged in varied patterns ranging from the compact to the dispersed type of distribution.

4.4 Betweenness Centrality (C_B)

In the network system, some of the nodes are more central rather than spatial distance, subject to their positions. Betweenness centrality also attempts to evaluate the criticality of a node in the network, with reference to the number of times a node is needed to be crossed through the shortest path in the network (Farhad and Ulfat 2019). Consequently the critical node therefore plays a mediating role between other nodes of the network. It also explains the role of third-party nodes for controlling the flow of information in the network. But in a network, the number of intermediary values may range from 0 to ∞ . The same principle is also applied by scholars, Wasserman and Faust (1994) and Oluwajana et al. (2012).

$$C_B = \sum_{s \neq v \neq t \in V} \frac{d(s, t|v)}{d(s, t)} \dots \dots \dots (iv)$$

where, $d(s, t|v)$ is the number of shortest paths that are available between s and t passing through the node v and, $d(s, t)$ is the total number of shortest paths that exist between s and t . The above analysis shows that betweenness centrality measure is a straightforward method to investigate the structure of network topology. The study identified that almost 64 per cent of the total

settlements that belongs to low and very low C_B classes. These settlements are therefore, considered insignificant (being between) for the flow of information. The distribution of low and very low C_B results called non-tree-edges (constant movement for crossing the nodes to and fro and cross edges) structure that yields minimum betweenness value. Thus, road segment between Seling and Aizawl (via Tuiral) is one of the important road segments in the whole network. Similarly, most of the highest betweenness values are observed along important road segments and ultimately these settlements are represented as major collection centres, dissemination centres, halting points and junctions, namely Seling, Tuiral, Aizawl, Keifang/Saitual and Darlawn. This measure determined the critical road segment/major roads, such as arterial roads, sub-arterial roads, and secondary roads (Figure 1d).

4.5 Eigenvector Centrality (C_E)

Eigenvector centrality measures the centrality of a node in a network based on the weighted sum of centralities of its neighbors (Jayaweera et al., 2017) or it measures the importance of a node based on its links with other central nodes (Wen et al., 2019). It defines the importance of a settlement through its connectivity to important settlements. Thus, the measure of eigenvector centrality in the network considers two important determinants such as firstly, the number of links or number of adjacency nodes and, secondly, the centrality values of adjacent nodes. This study applies the

eigenvector centrality measure to evaluate the degree of diffusion or dissemination of information, which then influences surrounding nodes. The following equation describes Eigenvector Centrality (C_E);

$$\lambda x = \sum_{j=1}^N a_{ij} x_j \dots \dots \dots (v)$$

where, A is the adjacency matrix for this graph; $a_{ij}=1$ if vertices i and j are connected by an edge and 0 if not, $Ax = \lambda x, i = 1, \dots, n$. then, λ denotes the largest eigenvalue of A and n is the number of vertices (Bonacich, 2007). Figure 2 (a) shows that there is a sharp declining trend of eigenvector centrality values between eigencentre and the next successive values indicate that the network is a centralised type of a network. The settlements with very high and high C_V are mainly confined in the middle part of the region, these towns and villages are strategically significant for the movement of information and the foundation of sustainable development in Aizawl district. The analysis also provides us to recognized which towns and villages serve as the hubs of networks that support the district long-term socio-economic sustainability.

4.6 Correlation of Centrality Measures

The correlation coefficient of centrality measures specified in the study has positive correlation in case of urban network in Aizawl district. In The strongest overall correlation among the centrality is experienced between C_C and C_E at $r=0.95$ followed by C_D and C_V correlation with $r=0.77$. On the other hand, the weakest positive correlation between centrality measures exists between C_D and C_E , and the correlation is also considered weak even though the correlation is positive ($r=0.25$). Degree of Centrality (C_D) and Eigenvector Centrality (C_V) are measures for neighborhood-based centrality, while Closeness Centrality (C_C), Betweenness centrality (C_B), and Eccentricity (C_E) are known as measures for shortest global/path-based centrality. Thus, the study also examines the degree of associations between these two categories. The lowest correlation was found between C_D (i.e. neighborhood-base/local centrality measure) and C_E (shortest path-base/global centrality measure). As for the correlation index, when the calculated value of global centrality measure increases the local centrality measures may increase with a limited value.

Table 1: Correlation Coefficient of Centrality Measures Index

Degree of Measures	Degree (C_D)	Eccentricity (C_E)	Closeness (C_C)	Betweenness (C_B)	Eigenvector (C_V)
Degree (C_D)	1.00				
Eccentricity (C_E)	0.25	1.00			
Closeness (C_C)	0.36	0.95	1.00		
Betweenness (C_B)	0.56	0.53	0.59	1.00	
Eigenvector (C_V)	0.77	0.37	0.56	0.48	1.00

4.7 Spatial Variations of Node Centrality within Centrality Classes

In the network centrality analysis, each of the centrality measures has a variety of topological structures and centrality patterns. Addressing the issue of the ‘sensitivity of the nodes’ the coefficient of variations of the centrality class reveals different characteristics. The level of dispersion around the mean of betweenness centrality measure is $r=115.83$ per cent, eigenvector is ranks second with a score of $r=78.87$ per cent, the degree of centrality third ($r=46.49$ per cent), closeness comes in the fourth position ($r=24.37$ per cent) and the least degree of variation is experienced in eccentricity ($r=17.82$ per cent). In the case of betweenness and eigenvector centrality measures the centrality between the settlements show a discrepancy in both the highest values and the minimum centrality values, which means that the distribution of centrality values are more inconsistent in these measurements. Comparing neighborhood-base and shortest path approaches (excluding betweenness), global-based centrality

measures have a least degree of variation because all the nodes exist in the network are considered for the centrality of a particular node (Table 2).

Table 2 shows that a very high degree of centrality class is associated with diversity within the class. For high and moderate classes in the network the centrality values are more compact and uniform, meaning that the coefficient of variation have declined in these two classes. On the other hand, the low centrality class has a higher degree of spatial variations of node centrality while some nodes falling under this category were very low due to the location and positional problems in the network. Normally very high degree of centrality class experience greater coefficient of variations than those high and moderate classes. For instance, in the betweenness centrality measure the spatial variation of centrality in the moderate class is $r=15.78$ per cent and increases to $r=34.27$ per cent. Again, in the very low degree class the increase is more than four times with $r=156.81$ per cent of spatial variation within the class. On the other hand, in the eccentricity measure, the

Table 2: Coefficient of Variation on Centrality Classes Index

Class	Centrality Measures (Coefficient of Variations in Per cent)				
	Degree	Closeness	Betweenness	Eigenvector	Eccentricity
Very High	0	6.10	23.71	38.76	6.11
High	0	3.80	10.41	13.91	3.36
Moderate	0	4.77	15.78	12.66	4.07
Low	0	5.61	34.27	12.87	4.04
Very Low	0	7.43	156.81	25.00	3.22
All	46.49	24.37	115.83	78.87	17.82

diversity of centrality is more in the higher degree classes than in the lower centrality classes. This means that high degree of centrality is confined to a few segments of the network and a larger portion of the nodes are least central in the network. On the whole, it can be said that an increasing trend of node centrality within the network leads to a diversified centrality pattern in general and a decline in node centrality leads to a diversified centrality pattern in particular. It can be said that the least degree of centrality results in an increase of spatial variability. In the hilly areas, the diversity pattern increases rapidly with an increase in the network connectivity pattern because of the nature of the hill topography which does not allow a uniform increase in the centrality levels.

4.8 Level of Nodes Centrality and Accessibility

Centrality measures as the key variables that are considered for the measurement of node accessibility (Hansen, 1959; Watts & Strogatz 1998; Barabási & Albert 1999; Hellervik et al. 2019; Sahitya & Prasad 2020). The study adopted the idea of synthesisation method to simplify the overall picture of node accessibility by simple statistical techniques called Mean Accessibility Index (A_I), which can be expressed by the following formula:

$$A_I = \sum_{i \geq 1}^n \left(\frac{C_{Di} + C_{Ci} + C_{Bi} + C_{Ei} + C_{Vi}}{\bar{X}Deg} \right) \times 100$$

where, A_I is mean accessibility index of i node, C_{Di} the weighted rank of i node in Degree of centrality measure, C_{Ci} is the

weighted rank of i node in Closeness centrality measure, C_{Bi} weighted rank of i node in Betweenness centrality measure, C_{Ei} weighted rank of i node in Eccentricity centrality measure, C_{Vi} weighted rank of i node in Eigenvector centrality measure and $\bar{X}Deg$ is the mean of Accessibility Index.

The analysis highlights the fact that nodes lying in the middle parts of the network are more accessible and has greater influence than those nodes lying in the north, south and north-eastern clusters of the network. The settlements of nodes in the low category are found in the north, south and north-eastern tips of the network. The least accessible nodes are also embodied in the dead-end-nodes. Structurally, the levels of accessibility of the nodes deviate/decline from the central part of the network towards the extreme north and southern parts of the network. The highest accessible node in the network is Seling with 218.20 A_I values, followed by Aizawl and Saitual. They are the most important transport junctions in the entire network system. It also revealed that the level of accessibility as denoted by A_I is determined by the amount of clusters controlled by the nodes or complexity of network. For, instance, Seling node has the highest degree of accessibility due to the fact that there is a direct link with clusters from the north and indirect connection with the southern and north eastern clusters. Aizawl city is a major administrative and commercial hub in the district. Other smaller settlements like Dilkhan, Tuirial, Khanpui and Sesawng are found in this

Figure 1: Spatial Distribution of (a) Degree of Centrality & (b) Degree of Eccentricity (c) Closeness Centrality and (d) Betweenness Centrality

Figure 2 : Spatial Distribution of (a) Eigenvector Centrality and (b) Mean Accessibility (A_1)

category due to their influences on their peripheral areas and their adjacency to high A_1 nodes (Figure 2b). It indicates that accessibility level of a particular settlement is highly determined by the location and position of the settlements or nodes in the network.

5. Conclusion

The study identified that the combination of geographical, historical, economic and social factors are important factors for the existence of road networks which in turn is very crucial for the location

of node centrality. It is found that the topological structure of road network in the study area is centralised network type as indicated by the hub and spoke organization model which is a part of centralized network. Seling and Aizawl are the central hubs of the network in the study area and offers a full array of services for the whole network. On the other hand, Sialsuk, and Keifang/Saitual vertices are acting as secondary establishments or hubs, offering a limited range of services for the low scoring nodes. In terms of interaction, the hubs

and spokes network system is a more efficient and facilitates optimum use of transport resources in the network. The study revealed that spatial distribution of nodes centrality is significantly determined by geographic centrality. Node centrality explains the nature of geographical centrality namely, global, local, isolated unit of centrality. All the very high and high centrality value nodes are confined to the central and middle parts of the network. These centrally located settlements are more influential in the flow of information through the network system. The results demonstrate the significance of centrality measures for critical probability of nodes with respect to the location and position of the node in the network. The models also demonstrate the efficiency and velocity of nodes for information dissemination on the basis of Euclidian distance (not dependent on geographic distance). On the other hand, both the location and position of node centrality determine heterogeneity and diversity of spatial/geographical centrality. But, the problem of the study lies in the fact that the study only adopted matrix distance to obtain relatively general results and facilitate its application. At some point geographical constraints and its attributes form complex geographical factors to control the network system e.g., topography, population and economy etc.

The nature of the topological structure is varied amongst the global and local centrality measures. Especially for global centrality measures like Closeness centrality, Betweenness centrality and

Eccentricity (i.e. very high and high class) are distributed in a longitudinal fashion which is primarily influenced by the arrangement of the road segments. Thus, geographical factors play a critical role in the segmentation of the road network and are associated with the spatial distribution of nodes or their alignment. In the context of local centrality measures like C_D and C_V , the critical nodes are distributed in compact forms and confined to a limited segment of the network. They are quantified as hubs or distribution center of the networks. The analysis found out that the low and very low degree classes are distributed in an irregular fashion, which points to the fact that the low scoring nodes are diverse in nature due to the influence of local and global factors. The correlation coefficient of centrality measures specifies the quality and quantity of relationship between the centrality measures. Table 1 show that all centrality measures have positive relationship. Between the centrality measures, local centrality measures are more associated than global centrality measures. On the other hand the lowest degree of correlation was observed between degree of centrality (local) and degree of eccentricity (global). Analysis of Coefficient of variation (C_V) shows that those nodes falling under low centrality categories experience greater diversity than those nodes under high centrality classes. This means that higher inequality exists within the lower classes, which is a consequence of the structural topology of the network. The study identified that important nodes and spatial distribution

of nodes in a systematic way. The study showed that the different concepts and measures of centrality are appropriate for identification and analysis of network centrality.

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